

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION ON DEBIT CARD SERVICES AMONG USERS IN POLLACHI TALUK

Dr. S. Shanmugapriya* & D. Kavya**

* Assistant Professor, PG & Research Department of Commerce, NGM College, Pollachi, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

** Full Time Research Scholar, PG & Research Department of Commerce, NGM College, Pollachi, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: Dr. S. Shanmugapriya & D. Kavya, "Customer Satisfaction on Debit Card Services Among Users in Pollachi Taluk", International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 151-155, 2018.

Copy Right: © IJCRME, 2018 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

One of the invention and application of the latest technology is credit cards and Debit cards. Credit card is a widely used source of conventional credit for restaurants, as well as telephone and television advertised products. In short credit cards act as a short – term loan. Along with the benefits some disadvantages are also attached with the credit cards. ATMs of many banks are nothing but virtual branches, as customers can conduct any transactions, through the touch screens. The objective of the study is to examine the practical problem face by the card holders and offer effective suggestion. The major findings of this study and suitable suggestions are presented in this article.

Key Words: Debit Card, ATM & Services

Introduction:

Banks are playing vital role in the Economic Development of a Country. A sound and effective banking system is the backbone of an economy. The emergence of private/new generation banks has been changed the entire banking operations drastically by the use of sophisticated new technologies like internet banking, ATMs (Automated Teller Machines), EFT (Electronic Fund Transfer), Debit cards, Credit cards, Mobile banking, etc., are accessible to customers on a 24x7 basis across the world. These modern technologies enable the bankers to overcome the barriers of time and space in extending their customer services.

Customer satisfaction has become very important know a days. Every organization whether offering product or services all are providing more or less same. But the difference lies only when the services of the organizations or product of the organizations are compared. In other words we can say that the satisfaction level of the customers or consumers of such product or services is tried to measure. Customer satisfaction is one of the key factor which leads to customer retention and customer loyalty or brand loyalty. As the technology is growing at fast pace, every organization has started using information technology to improve its efficiency and for time saving. Information technology has brought drastic change in Banking Industry. It has changed the entire scenario of banking organizations. All the conventional systems of banking were no more in the use. Now even you are maintaining your account with the bank in which you hardly visit to its branch for amount deposit or with drawl. This has become possible with the help of information technology and innovative products of technology. One of the gifts of information technology for banking customers are ATM stands for Automated Teller Machine. With the help of simple magnetic card you can with draw and deposit (available in limited banks) money anywhere. This has become possible only by the virtue of information technology.

Review of Literature:

Afroza Parvin et.al (2010) carried out a study entitle "Satisfaction on Debit Card user in Bangladesh: A Study on same private commercial banks" made an attempt to measure the satisfaction level of debit cards users of different private commercial banks and the major problems faced by the card user. C. Senthil Kumar in (2015) carried out a study on customer's perception towards debit card users in public and private sector banks at Dharmapuri district. The level of satisfaction of customer towards debit card. Total questionnaires are 110 and 80 were selected for sample size. Here the chi-square tool is used here to find the result. Gene Amromin and Suit Chakravotion (2007) in a debit card and cash usage: a cross country analysis, the larger demonization notes are affected in the people whole life. How they are changing the foreign currency to India by away. They used primary data. They used chi-square test and confined variable. In study electronic substitutes are able to reduce the demand for small demonization notes and coins because no change is required for these transaction.

Objectives of the Study:

The objectives of this study are as follows:

- ✓ To measure the satisfaction level of debit card users of different private commercial banks.
- ✓ To find out major problems faced by the card users.
- ✓ To recommend some policy measures for the better service delivery and customer retention with a view to achieving wealth maximization goal.
- ✓ To examine the practical problem face by the card holders and offer effective suggestions.

Research Methodology:

The present study focuses on the perception of consumers on debit card. It also makes an attempt to examine to what extent the consumers are making use of debit card. In order to execute the study, data have been collected from a select sample and appropriate statistical tools are employed to take out the information contained in the data so collected. This chapter clearly spells out the materials and methods developed in the study.

Sampling Technique:

Non probability – Convenience sampling Primary data are collected through convenience sampling technique, for getting the real picture of the study.

Non-probability sampling is that sampling procedure which does not afford any basis for estimating the probability that each item in the population has been included in the sample. Convenience sample is a sampling technique where the respondents are selected in a part or in whole at the convenience of the researcher.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Socio-Economic Profile:

S.No	Factors	No of Respondents	Percent
1	Area		
	Rural	69	53.1
	Urban	61	46.92
2.	Gender		
	Male	64	49.23
	Female	66	50.77
3.	Age		
	Below 20 Years	36	27.7
	21 – 30 Years	42	32.3
	31– 45 Years	28	21.5
	Above 45 Years	24	18.5
4.	Marital Status		
	Married	60	46.2
	Unmarried	70	53.8
5.	Educational Qualification		
	Illiterate	3	2.3
	Sslc	5	3.8
	Hsc	5	3.8
	Diploma	14	10.8
	Under Graduate	41	31.5
	Post Graduate	24	18.5
	Professional	19	14.6
	M.Phil./Phd	19	14.6
6.	Occupation		
	Agriculturist	36	27.7
	Businessman	19	14.6
	Government Employee	20	15.4
	Home Maker	6	4.6
	Private Sector Employee	15	11.5
	Professional	28	21.5
	Retired Person	6	4.6
	Student	36	27.7
7.	Type of Family		
	Joint	60	46.2
	Nuclear	70	53.8
8.	Number of Members		
	Two	12	9.2
	Three	26	20
	Four	58	44.6
	Above Four	34	26.2
9.	Number of Earning Members in the Family		
	One	31	23.85

	Two	56	43.08
	Three	30	23.08
	Above Three	13	10

The above table reveals that out of 130 respondents, 69(53.1%) belongs to Rural area and the rest 61(46.92%) belong to urban area. It is clear from the above table that out of the 130 respondents 64(49.23%) are female and the remaining 66(50.77%) are male. Out of 130 respondents, 36 (27.7%) respondents age group between 20 year, 42(32.3%) respondents are in the age group between 21-30 years and 28(21.5%) respondents are in the age group between 31 – 45 years and the rest 24(18.5)respondents are in the age group of above 45 years. Out of 130 respondents, 60(46.2%) are married and rest 70(53.8%) are unmarried of using debit card services. Out of the 130 respondents 5(3.8%) are completed SSLC, 3(2.3%) of the respondents are HSC, 5(3.8%) of the respondents are Diploma, 14(10.8%) of the respondents are under graduate and 41(31.5%) of the respondents are post graduate remaining 24(18.5%) of the respondents are post gradates and 19(14.6%) of the respondents are professional 19(14.6%) of the respondents are M.Phil./PhD. Out of the 130 respondents, 36(27.7%) are Agriculturist, 19(14.6%) respondents are doing Business, 20(15.4%) respondents are respondents employed in government sector, 6(4.6%) respondents are home maker and 15(11.5%) of the respondents are private sector employees and the remaining 28(21.5)respondents are professionals, 6(4.6%) respondents are retired person and remaining 36(27.7%) are students for using debit card services. Out of the 130 respondents, 60(46.2%) respondents are in joint family 70(53.8%) respondents are in nuclear family. Out of 130 respondents 12(9.2%) of the respondents are belong to 2 members, 26(20%) of the respondents are belong to 3 members, 58(44.6%) of the respondents are belong to 4 members and 34(26.2%) of the respondents are belong to above 5 members. Out of 130 respondents 31(23.85%) of the respondents have 1 earning members in their family, 56(43.08%) of the respondents have 2 earning members in their family and remaining 30(23.08%) of the respondents have 3 earning members in their family 13(10%) of the respondents have above 3.

Level of Satisfaction:

S.No	Variables	Highly Satisfied (%)	Satisfied (%)	Neither Satisfied Nor Dissatisfied (%)	Dissatisfied (%)	Highly Dissatisfied (%)
1.	Security	58.5	21.5	11.5	0.8	7.7
2.	Service charges	11.5	40	28.5	10.0	10.0
3.	Respondents service	26.9	20.0	22.3	18.5	12.3
4.	Convenience	20	33.7	23.1	15.4	8.5
5.	Time	35.4	29.2	18.5	9.2	7.7
6.	Pin Number	26.2	25.4	30.0	11.5	6.9
7.	24*7 Access	25.4	23.8	27.7	12.3	10.8
8.	Validity	19.2	27.7	32.3	11.5	9.2
9.	Master visa card	25.4	17.7	38.5	8.5	10.0
10.	Privacy	18.5	26.2	28.5	18.6	8.5

The above table reveals that out of 130 respondents, (58.5%) are highly satisfied on the security of using debit card services, (21.5%) are satisfied with the security, (11.5%) of the respondents are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, (0.8%) of the respondents are dissatisfied on security and (7.7%) respondents are highly dissatisfied on security of using debit card service. The above table shows that Out of 130 respondents, (11.5%) are highly satisfied on the service chargers of using debit card services, (40%) are satisfied with the security, (28.5%) of the respondents are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, (10%) of the respondents are dissatisfied on security and (10%) respondents are highly dissatisfied on service chargers of using debit card service. It is clear from the above table that out of 130 respondents, (26.9%) are highly satisfied on the respondents service of using debit card services, (20%) are satisfied with the security, (22.3%) of the respondents are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, (18.5%) of the respondents are dissatisfied on security and (12.3%) respondents are highly dissatisfied on respondents service of using debit card service. It could be seen from the table out of 130 respondents, (20%) are highly satisfied on the convenience of using debit card services, (33.7%) are satisfied with the security, (23.1%) of the respondents are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, (15.4%) of the respondents are dissatisfied on security and (8.5%) respondents are highly dissatisfied convenience of using debit card service. It is evident from the above table Out of 130 respondents, (35.4%) are highly satisfied on the time of using debit card services, (29.2%) are satisfied with the security, (18.5%) of the respondents are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, (9.2%) of the respondents are dissatisfied on security and (7.7%) respondents are highly dissatisfied on time of using debit card service. Out of 130 respondents, (26.2%) are highly satisfied on the pin number of using debit card services, (25.4%) are satisfied with the security, (30%) of the respondents are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, (11.5%) of the respondents are dissatisfied on security and (6.9%) respondents are highly dissatisfied on pin number of using debit card service. Out of 130 respondents, (25.4%) are highly

satisfied on the 24*7 access of using debit card services, (23.8%) are satisfied with the security, (27.7%) of the respondents are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, (12.7%) of the respondents are dissatisfied on security and (10.8%) respondents are highly dissatisfied on 24*7 access of using debit card service. Out of 130 respondents, (19.2%) are highly satisfied on the validity of using debit card services, (27.7%) are satisfied with the security, (32.3%) of the respondents are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, (11.5%) of the respondents are dissatisfied on security and (9.2%) respondents are highly dissatisfied on validity of using debit card service. Out of 130 respondents, (25.4%) are highly satisfied on the acceptance of master visa card of using debit card services, (17.7%) are satisfied with the security, (38.5%) of the respondents are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, (8.5%) of the respondents are dissatisfied on security and (10%) respondents are highly dissatisfied on acceptance of master visa card of using debit card service. Out of 130 respondents, (18.5%) are highly satisfied on the privacy of using debit card services, (26.2%) are satisfied with the security, (28.5%) of the respondents are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, (18.6%) of the respondents are dissatisfied on security and (8.5%) respondents are highly dissatisfied on privacy of using debit card service.

Findings:

Socio-Economic Profile of Sample Users:

- ✓ Most of the respondents, 69(53.1%) belong to rural areas.
- ✓ Majority of 42(32.3%) the respondents belong to the age group of up to 21 - 30 years.
- ✓ Majority of 66(50.77%) the respondents are female.
- ✓ Majority of 70(53.8%) the debit card users are unmarried.
- ✓ Majority of 41(31.5%) the respondents are under graduates.
- ✓ Majority of respondents, 36(27.7%) occupation are Agriculturist.
- ✓ Majority of 70(53.8%), the respondents are nuclear family.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents, 58(44.6%) have four members in their family.
- ✓ Majority of 56(43.08%) the respondents have two earning members in their family.
- ✓ Majority of 39(30%) the respondents family monthly income is up to Rs. 20,001 – Rs.40,000

Suggestions:

- ✓ More of the ATM centers should be opened especially at important place of the city and outside the city.
- ✓ Create more awareness among the customers about the depositing cheque/cash through ATM which facilitates to reduce work burden of the bank branches.
- ✓ The debit card is used only as a substitute for ATM cards. There is no awareness among the customers about the other user like shopping, online shopping, Bills payment and online recharge. The customers should made aware about these services.
- ✓ Most of the banks are maximum allowing three withdrawals between tie up banks that should be increased more. In future, all the public sector, private sector and foreign banks should create tie up among themselves for the withdrawals of cash through ATMs without any service chargers or any restrictions.
- ✓ All banks should also take necessary action to promote all of their modern operations through proper media of advertising. Extensive and aggressive advertising is must for capturing stable position among the public.

Conclusion:

Debit cards look like credit cards or ATM (Automated Teller Machine) cards, but operate like cash or personal cheque. Debit cards are different from credit cards. While a credit card is away to “pay later”, a debit card is a “pay now”. When you use a debit card, your money is quickly deducted from your checking or saving account. But the customers are still now our aware of new program offered by banks like depositing money, fund transfer, instant money transfer (IMT), cheque book request, paying bill, mobile recharge etc. which are specially offered by private sector banks. The banker must also cancel extra charges for their special service provided to customers. The suggestions are implemented properly to improve the both public and private sector banks services to the customers.

References:

1. Bhargava, S. (2004). Debit cards: A rule generation plastic money. Chartered financial analyst. Jan. 47-50.
2. Carow and Kenneth, A.S. (1999). Debit card, or cash: survey evidence on gasoline Purchases. Journal of economics and business. Sept-Oct. 51(5):409-21.
3. Cherion, G. (2002). Come Dec, debit cards will overtake credit card. Economic time, 3 august.
4. Mookerjivedita (1999). A debit card is a product of the future. Financial express, 16 may.
5. Vyas, H.P. (2001). Consumers’ satisfaction measurement in using plastic money, The Indian journal of commerce, 54(3) July-Sep: 53-64.
6. Amromine, Eugene, and Sujit Chakravorti. “Debit card and cash usage: a cross-country analysis,” working paper WP 2007-04, Federal Reserve Bank of Chicago.

7. www.sbi.com
8. www.sbi.co.in
9. www.google.com
10. www.wikipedia.com
11. www.yahoo.com
12. www.bing.com
13. www.msn.com
14. www.researcherworid.com